

Modeling Changing Scientific Concepts with Complex Networks: A Case Study on the Chemical Revolution

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1780

1800

MOTIVATION | Concepts as complex networks

GOAL | Explain conceptual change in scientific discourse

To what extent do complex networks reflect the spread and competition of concepts in the Chemical Revolution?

INPUT. Royal Society Corpus from the 1750s to 1800s mentioning keywords
<https://fedora.clarin-d.uni-saarland.de/rsc/access.html>

OUTPUT. Complex networks for each period that capture the core-periphery organization of concepts

METHODS. Framework has 4 stages:

- sampling Kullback-Leibler Divergence
- topic modeling Latent Dirichlet Allocation
- network building Jensen-Shannon distance
- clustering Hierarchical Agglomerative Clustering, Louvain Algorithm

FINDINGS | Increased entropy and topological density accompany onomasiological change

Although #nodes starts and ends similarly, #edges more than doubled

While #communities and modularity decline, percolation and #edges rise

TAKEAWAYS

Network dynamics effectively map conceptual change where entropy-diversity of ideas & network metrics-stability of communication

This improves interpretability in language modeling and prevents bias augmentation while working with historical sparse data